

Towards an Ecosystem of Instruments of Tunable Machine Learning

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Abstract

This paper introduces an embedded machine learning framework that integrates machine learning model training, tuning and control within live musical performance. Responding to critiques of disembodied and disempowering ML tools, we propose an ecosystem of Musically Embodied Machine Learning (MEML): low-resource, self-contained devices providing real-time machine learning on control data. We detail two open-source board designs, a firmware stack featuring a C++ library for on-device training of small networks (with focus on reinforcement learning) and an Arduino library that unifies real-time audio, sensor I/O and ML tasks. Two reference instruments—a joystick-driven FM synthesiser using interactive ML and a reinforcement-learning variant—illustrate rapid prototyping and pedagogical value. The framework is being iteratively refined through university workshops and ongoing collaborations with professional musicians, who shape its future direction.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have had a huge impact in the community of musical research. Generative AI is now ubiquitous in music production and content generation; however, a substantial amount of research has also involved musical instruments and musical gestures (Visi and Tanaka, 2021). The use of ML in musical instruments invites some compelling design challenges. When creating ML models that are used in musical instruments, the designers and musicians are typically working between two very different styles of interface: the instrument itself and data science environments, such as a Python notebook. This creates a disembodied split, which arguably precludes the workflow of the musical performance. But what if the full processes of engaging with machine learning were built into an instrument, so that the instrument itself is the interface to ML? What if the instrument controlled aspects of training, inference, data curation and model curation in a musical way?

In this paper, we introduce the concept of Musically Embodied Machine Learning (MEML), in which machine learning is made available to the musician as a tangible object that can be manipulated as part of the artistic performance or practice. The main part of this paper will be the presentation of the MEML framework, consisting of a set of libraries that support embedded microcontrollers for the on-device training and tuning of ML models, with a focus on reinforcement learning. Finally, we discuss our method to validate the MEML framework with the community of makers and musicians, through ongoing longitudinal studies and a series of workshops. Through these elements, we aim to foster the creation of the MEML ecosystem, intended as the interrelated network of devices, software, users, and musical output that revolves around an artist-centred and tangible way of experiencing ML and AI in musical performance.

1.1 Motivation

Musicians are arguably experts in embodied interaction, especially considering the rich complexity of musical gestures (Jack et al., 2017; Buxton, 1997), however this fact is rarely reflected in AI-based interfaces for musicians. Current AI advances typically involve large language models running on a client-server infrastructure, generating sophisticated outputs from a (often text-based) prompt. Vigliensoni and Fiebrink (2025) note that, among other things, these models force a type and style of low-bandwidth interaction that is “often not conducive to musical creativity”, a thesis supported by Wang (2025). The paradigm of interactive machine learning (Visi and Tanaka, 2021) is an established alternative, giving performers the ability to map gestures and create their own performance vocabulary. Nonetheless, the laptop is still the medium to access those tools, with the consequence that interaction with the machine learning process as a whole can still feel disembodied due to the dissonance between laptop and instrument. There is the occasion to develop interfaces that harness the sensorimotor abilities of all musicians, for engagement with machine learning with a unified interface, embodied within a musical instrument.

1.2 Musically Embodied Machine Learning

To this end, we introduce Musically Embodied Machine Learning (MEML) and the related concept of Instruments of Tunable Machine Learning (ITML). They build upon the concepts of embedded AI (Pelinski et al., 2022) and the larger field of ‘small’ or ‘edge’ AI, but they spell two further important requirements. Firstly, there’s a focus on the instrument being *embodied*: both in the sense of being manifest in the everyday world (Dourish, 1999), and of working with and for the human body in its many forms (Homewood et al., 2021). Then, the machine learning needs to be *tunable* within the instrument: model training, inference, data curation and model curation happen on the device, within the context of real-time musical interaction. Therefore, we strive to create instruments that are embedded, self-contained, support real-time interactive patterns with ML, and allow for on-the-fly training and tuning as part of musical practice.

2 Related work

2.1 Interactive machine learning

Interactive machine learning (IML) systems are described (Visi and Tanaka, 2021; Fiebrink et al., 2009) as involving gesture sensing, gesture recognition, feature extraction and ML mapping, in many cases to a synthesis engine. The field of IML is well-established and familiar to the machine learning community since the Wekinator (Fiebrink et al., 2009). The interactivity of IML is expressed in two ways: it’s machine learning *of interaction*, as gestures are used to interact with the digital, and *with interaction*, since the act of training the model is itself an interactive process. Recent developments involve the use of reinforcement learning to make the training and use of the ML models more seamless (Visi and Tanaka, 2020).

The maturity of IML allowed researchers like Fiebrink (Fiebrink and Sonami, 2020; Vigliensoni and Fiebrink, 2025) to reflect on the use of ML in NIME and other instrumental performances. The way data is perceived and manipulated is different in musical IML to other application of ML/AI: from a ‘groundtruth’ containing a fixed representation of a phenomenon, it becomes an active medium that the musician interacts with (Vigliensoni and Fiebrink, 2025). Concepts like ‘error’ and ‘inaccuracy’ also shift their meaning towards sources of dialogue and creativity. Data does not have to be infinitely large and universally representative, and models do not have to be infinitely accurate and infallible (Vigliensoni et al., 2022).

As an example, Gianluca Elia (Elia, 2025) discusses his use of machine learning within his digitally controlled no-input mixer (Elia and Overholt, 2024):

Making the maps is then part of the relationships between the instrument and the player, involving the selection of sounds for the training set, experimentation with different ways and criterias to organize them, practice with the produced control interfaces, and evaluation of their features and afforded expressiveness. These iterations could also be performed live, as a continuous process in which the

affordances of the instrument evolve while it's being played, informed by each new sound produced and the way they are played by the musician.

2.2 ML in instruments and performance

Machine learning has been incorporated into a wide range of musical uses and musical instruments. The Wekinator is the basis for many performances with custom interfaces, Sonami’s *Spring Spyre* (Fiebrink and Sonami, 2020) being one of the latest. RAVE (Caillon and Esling, 2021) and DDSP (Engel et al., 2020) allow ML-based timbre transfer and audio re-synthesis to be used in real-time performance; their release fostered an ecosystem of models (Intelligent Instruments Lab, 2023; neutone.ai, 2022) and performances (Armitage et al., 2023; Stefani et al., 2024).

Musical instruments integrating ML/AI are sometimes based on the above technological paradigms, embedding them into a coherent design and exposing a particular characteristic or pre-trained implementation of a given ML model. Certain smart guitars (Lähdeoja, 2009; Martelloni et al., 2023) and percussion instruments (Turchet et al., 2018; Jathal, 2017) reproduce the gesture-to-sound classification model on top of the acoustic instrument, juxtaposing a ‘digital’ identity to the acoustic body and using expert musical interaction to design the mapping model. The limitations of this approach are the lack of flexibility in the data (assumed pre-determined and immutable) and the model, supervised to learn a similarly pre-determined and immutable vocabulary at the expense of other aspects of performance.

A growing number of instruments harness RAVE (Privato et al., 2024; Shepardson and Magnusson, 2023) or DDSP (Bessel’s Trick¹; Shier et al., 2024) for re-synthesis or exploration of latent dimensions. They replace the experience of a pre-determined mapping with the exploration of sometimes idiosyncratic regions of the latent dimensions. This idiosyncrasy is often perceived as ‘otherness’, with the ML model making its presence known; many performances embrace this concept of dueting with the machine, and build the performance around a duet (Stefani et al., 2024) or a call-and-response². This otherness is perceived as eerie, as the concept of Hauntology in musical AI demonstrates (Privato and Magnusson, 2024). The community of feedback musicians has integrated ML into feedback instruments that are already meant to have a degree of agency (Visi, 2024; Elia and Overholt, 2024).

This short survey identifies how immutability and inflexibility is a major limitation in ML instruments, balanced by the use of AI for black-box exploratory performance that is embraced by particular musical communities. The sense of ‘otherness’ given by the ML algorithm could also be linked to models running on equipment external to the instrument, predominantly a laptop, symbolising a disembodied and displaced centre of ‘thinking’ that intervenes, sometimes invasively, in the performance.

2.3 Embedded ML libraries

Table 1: Comparison of embedded machine learning frameworks

Framework	Language	Target runtime	On-device training	Reinforcement learning	License
AIfES	C for embedded	Bare metal or RTOS	Yes, feed-forward training	Yes, user-coded RL	AGPL or commercial
Rust Burn	Rust (no_std)	Bare metal or OS	Yes, autodiff included	Yes, custom RL code	MIT/Apache 2.0
Alibaba MNN	C++ multi-language	Android, Linux	iOS, Partial on-device training	Possible with custom RL	MIT (free)
TinyDNN	C++14 header-only	Bare metal or OS	Yes, SGD/Adam	with Yes, user-coded RL	BSD 3-Clause

¹<https://fcaspe.github.io/BesselsTrick/>

²From Laetitia Sonami’s keynote at the AAU-CPH MEML workshop on 15/01/2025, yet unpublished.

If the objective is to design an embodied experience of ML within the musical instrument, what are the currently available options? Investigating which solutions could support such a design effort, we identified five requirements that one such platform must satisfy:

1. Be *embedded/embodied*: it must run on low-power and low-cost edge devices.
2. Be *tunable*: inference and training need to run on-device and in real time.
3. Support *interactivity*: the design of embedded interfaces should be streamlined and easily accessible.
4. Support *reinforcement learning*: following Visi and Tanaka (2021); Scurto et al. (2021), it should encourage efforts in the exploration of reinforcement learning for musical interfaces.
5. Support *free replicability and diffusion*: it should not impose barriers on the reproduction of DMI designs; it should support uses in educational settings.

Many common ML/DL libraries for deployment at the edge (e.g. Tensorflow Lite Micro, ARM CMSIS-NN, Qualcomm SNPE) do not support on-device training. Devices like the Nvidia Jetson Nano and the Raspberry Pi, with or without neural hardware accelerators, would in principle perform both training and inference at the edge; significant disadvantages are their power consumption and the \$100+ cost of the hardware.

Table 1 highlights the four currently available DNN libraries that come closest to satisfying the requirements to build an ITML. They all support on-device training, and all but Alibaba MNN support an environment without an operating system, such as a bare-metal microcontroller. Fraunhofer’s AIFES is particularly attractive for its Arduino support; however, its semi-commercial licence severely restricts the replicability and diffusion of new musical instruments. Lastly, no library provides any explicit support for reinforcement learning; moreover, beyond library documentation and simple examples, no library offers a comprehensive set of example applications to aid diffusion and uptake in educational settings.

3 The MEML framework

Our review of current ML frameworks identifies a niche for a hardware and software framework specifically made for the design and the diffusion of ITMLs. We satisfy this niche through the development of our own framework for building ML apps, using embedded C++ on readily available microcontrollers. Our development effort is comprised of four elements:

- A **machine learning library**, *meMLP*, providing a simple API to build and train a multi-layer perceptron, with out-of-the-box support for RL scenarios.
- A **hardware platform** based on the RP2350 chip, the microcontroller in the Raspberry Pi Pico 2. We propose some open hardware designs for a versatile hardware interface, the *MEMLNaut*.
- A modular **application library**, *memllib*, to aid the development of applications on the RP2350 and MEMLNaut platforms.
- Two **example applications**, which show different ways to tune an FM synthesiser: with an interactive machine learning paradigm, and with a reinforcement learning paradigm.

3.1 The meMLP library

Our embedded ML library, *meMLP*, is a fork of David Nogueira’s *MLP* on GitHub³, adapted to be C++14-compliant and compatible with bare-metal environments. Currently, the library is built and tested on the Linux PC platform, the RP2350 chip, and the XMOS Xcore.ai⁴.

At its core, the library features all the functionality to train a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) on the target processor, with on-target unit tests to ensure robustness and good development practices. In addition to Nogueira’s effort, the library was expanded following the algorithms in Kinsley and

³<https://github.com/davidalbertonogueira/MLP>

⁴<https://www.xmos.com/xcore-ai>

Kukiela (2020) to cover the fundamental functionality of a modern ML library with support for RL, and in particular the Soft Actor-Critic paradigm (Haarnoja et al., 2018).

The library provides the three important components of a ML experiment:

- A **dataset class** is provided to manage, store, manipulate, and supply labelled data to a ML model.
- A **replay memory** class serves a similar purpose in a RL scenario, with functionality to store snapshots of the (s, a, r, s', d') states, transitions, and rewards in reinforcement learning in a replay buffer.
- The **MLP** class is the definition of a neural network model, consisting of a deep network of fully-connected layers with linear, ReLU, sigmoid, or *tanh* activation functions. The MLP class also has a built-in training loop, supporting mean-squared error and binary cross-entropy losses, and full-batch, mini-batch or stochastic gradient descent. Gradient update functions that are useful in RL were also implemented, such as an autograd-like `CalcGradients()` method to calculate policy gradients, and a smooth weight update for target agents.

This ML library is particularly well suited for the manipulation and mapping of control data, either from tangible interfaces and sensor signals (joysticks, accelerometers, etc...), or from features extracted from audio data through machine listening (loudness, spectral brightness...).

GitHub: <https://github.com/MusicallyEmbodiedML/memlp>

3.2 The MEMLNaut hardware

Figure 1: SensorBoard (left) connecting to the MEMLNaut (right).

The hardware platform that was chosen for the development of the MEML ecosystem was the RP2350 by Raspberry Pi: itself a sub-\$1 chip, it can also be bought in a number of different hardware configurations, the most popular of which is the Pi Pico 2 for \$6. This new iteration of the Raspberry Pi Pico contains two ARM Cortex-M33 cores clocked at 150 Mhz, supporting stable overclock up to 300 Mhz; both cores have a hardware floating-point unit. The compiler and driver stack is well-maintained and compatible with modern C++, and the platform also offers compatibility with the Arduino framework.

The basic setup to be productive with our MEML framework is:

- A \$6 **Raspberry Pi Pico 2**
- A \$9 **Teensy 4 audio shield** (rev D)

All our code was designed to run on this \$15 hardware platform, which can be battery-powered and has a small footprint suitable for unobtrusive digital modifications of musical instruments. The

low cost and versatility makes it an ideal platform for classes and workshops. There are, however, several hardware projects incorporating the RP2350 into boards that offer more I/O, memory, or other specific capabilities. One such device is the **MEMLNaut**, a unit designed to be a flexible development platform for ITMLs. The MEMLNaut includes a programmable RP2350 within a custom PCB including the same codec as the Teensy audio shield, a 5-pin DIN interface for MIDI, an SD card reader, a touchscreen display, three two-way momentary switches, three two-way toggle switches, three potentiometers, and one four-axis joystick. The board designs and bill of materials of the MEMLNaut are publicly available as a KiCad project, so that users can manufacture units according to their need. Another useful board design that we have made available is the SensorBoard, incorporating eight manually tunable ADCs to read analogue sensors and interfacing with either the Pi Pico 2 or the MEMLNaut via UART. Both boards are pictured in Figure 1.

MEMLNaut GitHub: <https://github.com/MusicallyEmbodiedML/MEMLNaut>

SensorBoard GitHub: <https://github.com/MusicallyEmbodiedML/MEMLSensorBoard>

3.3 The software framework

We built a set of helper classes and functions around the Arduino API with *arduino-pico*⁵, to lower the entry barrier for novice embedded developers and enable the use of documentation and support within the Arduino ecosystem.

Figure 2: System diagram of *memllib*. The blue (darker) rectangles are helper classes, the white rectangles are stub base classes that the user expands with ML or audio processing functionality.

Figure 2 illustrates the system-level architecture of *memllib*, the library that contains our helper classes. Core 0 of the RP2350 is tasked with running the I/O and machine learning tasks, whereas Core 1 interfaces with the audio codec and therefore runs the audio processing and machine listening routines. The library offers two abstraction layer written from either the MEMLNaut or a pre-defined hardware configuration on the Pi Pico 2; the SensorBoard’s UART communication is also handled in this library. Finally, a MIDI output and a SLIP-encoded UART output interface is provided for communication with external hardware or other microcontrollers.

The two base classes that the developer of ITMLs extends to implement custom functionality are:

⁵<https://github.com/earlephilhower/arduino-pico>

- **InterfaceBase**: this base class receives input data from either the MEMLNaut or the Pico 2's IO, from the Sensor Board's UART interface, or from the AnalysisParams received by the AudioAppBase's machine listening routine. The output of the processing function, which is meant to implement the ML model, is then sent to a UART interface, to the MIDI output, and to the AudioApp to modify audio processing parameters.
- **AudioAppBase**: this base class implements the real-time audio processing routines to either synthesise or modify sound, and perform machine-listening analysis. *memllib* also offers an FFT engine and the Maximilian audio DSP library (Grierson, 2012) for advanced audio effects or audio analysis.

GitHub: <https://github.com/MusicallyEmbodiedML/memllib>

3.4 Example Instruments

The last element in our proposed framework is a set of example applications, which serve as an introduction to all the other components of this framework. As our system allows for different interfaces to be mapped to different audio processing applications, we made one example audio application, a frequency-modulation (FM) synthesiser with four FM operators implemented with the Maximilian DSP library, exposing 14 parameters to be controlled by a ML algorithm. The effects of the ML model changing the weights are audible in the timbral variations of the relatively unconstrained FM synthesis; this allows to build a working relationship with the MEML interface intuitively, regardless of musical ability. The example processing application is accompanied by two ML interfaces: one that incorporates a common interactive ML workflow, and one that exemplifies an application of reinforcement learning.

Figure 3: Interaction diagram of the two interfaces, one running interactive ML, one running interactive RL.

3.4.1 Interactive ML interface

This application implements an interactive machine learning workflow reminiscent of the Wekinator (Fiebrink et al., 2009). A single neural network expects three ADC (joystick) readings as inputs, and it maps those to the output parameters of the audio processing app through two 10-neuron hidden layers with ReLU activation; the output has sigmoid activation to keep the range within (0, 1). One toggle switches between **training** and **inference** mode. In inference mode, any movement of the joystick is mapped to parameters according to the current weights in real-time. The ‘training mode’ enables the creation of examples in the dataset; the network is then trained to perform regression to fit the *ADC reading* \rightarrow *output parameters* dataset.

Figure 3a shows how the training mode enables the creation of examples in the dataset and trains the network. "Zooming into" the weights allows the finer exploration of parameters and sounds. The zoom-in mode triggers one of three user-switchable algorithms:

1. **Add noise** - add a small amount of Gaussian noise to current weights.
2. **Pre-train** - lightly train random weights so that the last parameters produced by the NN are associated to the centre position of the joystick.
3. **Zoom-in** - scale the movement of the joystick down to a small area around the last joystick position.

This workflow starts with user exploration of the parameter space through a randomised neural network; the random parameter space can be explored more finely by restraining the area that the joystick can explore through the ‘zoom-in’ function. The user is then able to create and curate a dataset of good outcomes out of this exploration. This workflow also enables interesting ways to interact with the model, such as training the network multiple times after adding more points to the dataset and creating dataset examples directly from an already trained model.

GitHub: <https://github.com/MusicallyEmbodiedML/fmsynthml>

Video demo: <https://youtu.be/WwQUQ8NdoSs>

3.4.2 Reinforcement learning interface

We are also providing an interface that incorporates a simplified reinforcement learning model. The system implements Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) (Lillicrap et al., 2015), a type of Soft Actor-Critic algorithm designed for continuous spaces, adapted to map input parameters such as joystick movements to audio processing or synthesis parameters. The system is comprised of an *actor* network mapping states (joystick inputs) to continuous actions (audio parameters), a *critic* network learning to estimate the expected future rewards for the current agent’s policy, and their respective target networks (*targetActor* and *targetCritic*) updated at a slower rate to stabilise training. Unlike a typical DDPG algorithm, this implementation omits the concepts of ‘done’ or ‘episode’, as the whole musical performance is supposed to be one arbitrarily long episode; moreover, the action of the agent does not change the state of the system, which is the user-controlled position of the joystick.

The RL algorithm, summarised in Figure 3b, is mapped to the joystick, one momentary toggle, and two potentiometers of the MEMLNaut. In addition, two timers will ‘tick’ to progress with exploration and optimisation respectively. The user of the ITML can listen to the model’s mappings by moving the joystick. Unlike the IML example above, the mappings aren’t static, but they drift according to the exploration noise, whose speed can be controlled by one potentiometer. The reward is a YES/NO input coming from the momentary toggle. The optimisation, which trains both the critic and the actor, runs on a timer whose frequency is set by the second potentiometer. This adaptation of the DDPG algorithm incorporates training seamlessly into the performance, blurring the line between a ‘training’ and ‘inference’ state, and letting the ML algorithm and the user come to a point of convergence during the performance itself.

GitHub: <https://github.com/MusicallyEmbodiedML/fmsynthrl>

Video demo: <https://youtu.be/NuQU5FpXnSM>

4 Validation

We are assessing the ability of our framework to support the quick prototyping of ITMLs in a variety of contexts, the ability for people of different technical or musical backgrounds to come to a productive relationship with ITMLs, and the usefulness of the MEML platform as a teaching tool for machine learning concepts.

We are validating these objectives in four ways:

1. **Self-reflexive practice** (Carey and Johnston, 2016) incorporating ITMLs in our own musical practice.
2. Use MEMLNaut as a platform for **probe instruments** (Tahiroğlu et al., 2020), to send to different musical practitioners.
3. Collaborate with musicians in **longitudinal user studies** involving the design of bespoke ITMLs.
4. **Workshops** or hackathons in educational settings, aimed at the quick prototyping or trial of ITMLs.

4.1 First workshop

Figure 4: Participants of the pilot workshop showcasing their prototypes at the end of the sessions.

The efforts in gathering data from probe instruments and long-form studies are ongoing; however, workshops are a good way to test and improve the suitability of the code for quick development and prototyping by a pool of people from different backgrounds. As an example, we briefly summarise the results and the challenges from the first MEML workshop, which took place in January 2025 at AAU-CPH in Copenhagen.

The three-day course was attended by 14 PhD and MSc students, mostly with technical backgrounds in music technology or acoustics, confident in Python-based AI and ML and with varying degrees of experience with C++ or electronics. After an introduction to the concepts of embedded ML and MEML, they were guided through simple tasks to gain familiarity with the Pi Pico 2, the Arduino environment, and the MEML code base. Over the remaining two days, the students were divided into groups and were tasked with designing and prototyping either a musical instrument or the modification/augmentation of a musical instrument, helped by the workshop’s organisers. On the closing evening, after a demonstration of the prototypes (Figure 4), the participants were gathered together in a World Café discussion (Fouché and Light, 2011) to reflect on different aspects of designing and making music with ITMLs. The outcome of the World Café exercise was a collection of four mindmaps, focussing on the barrier of entry for MEML, the challenges and opportunities of ML in musical instruments, and the important or desirable qualities in ML instruments.

4.2 Feedback and challenges

The participants reported that the approach that they developed in designing and playing ITMLs is different to the one that they would have when approaching a machine learning problem in Python.

ITMLs encourage quick and spontaneous interaction with the models, with creative rather than strictly scientific intent, similar to Collins et al’s *hybrinity* (Collins et al., 2020) or Broad et al’s *network bending* (Broad et al., 2021). This attitude seems to correlate with a serendipitous and glitchy type of aesthetic in performance, which according to our participants is ideally suited to experimental electronic genres, in a reference to Privato’s AI hauntology (Privato and Magnusson, 2024). A desire was expressed to find suitable constraints for the models so that they could be adapted to more types of instrumental practice.

However, the most significant challenge still lay in the steep learning curve that the embedded C++ platform poses to programmers and computer scientists who have predominantly experienced ML and coding through Python. As a result, most participants limited themselves to small edits to supplied example code to build their instruments. The issue lies not only in learning a new and statically-typed language, but also in the different mindset and the different set of concepts when programming ITMLs: real-time audio sample manipulation, latency constraints, and limited computational resources. We integrated some of the feedback from this workshop in the current version of the MEML framework: we restructured the code into classes with extensive documentation which make for a higher-level experience in coding, overloading base class methods rather than starting from the main loops at the system level. The examples were also expanded to showcase more minimal, reusable, and expandable scenarios and aid prototyping by modification of existing code.

5 Discussion

By releasing and sharing the the MEML software framework, we to provide a tool for the intuitive and organic exploration of the possibilities of machine learning within musical instruments, which can then be seen as music-making devices and machine learning interfaces at the same time. By encouraging makers and developers to adopt this library, we hope to open up a new way of understanding ML, and foster a community that disseminates this new understanding of ML in a growing number of musical and artistic applications.

5.1 An artist-in-the-loop ML experience

The most promising characteristic of ITMLs is the ability to make ML *tangible* to the musician: a model can be manipulated and interacted with in the same way as a synthesiser or a pedalboard; however, the ability to prototype many different interfaces extends this tangibility to textiles, wearables, and many other interfaces to be conceived around, or adapted to, the practice of music and dance.

The MEML framework also allows the investigation of one of the crucial problems of ML in an embodied interface: which training methods and interfaces effectively support human-in-the-loop real-time ML in musical applications? The approach followed by the Wekinator, as well as Mogeos (Zamborlin, 2015) among many others, seems to be a standard when building such interfaces. However, we showcase that a simple implementation of reinforcement learning can also be a way to a creative relationship with a ML model that seamlessly integrates with musical performance. As the project progresses, different interfaces will be developed, tested, and released, and more data will be available to assess what are good tangible interfaces for ML. An example that is being investigated is the use of the joystick-based interface to abstract the many parameters of external software and hardware synthesisers, beyond the abstraction of internal synthesis engines such as the FM synth in the above demonstrations.

Finally, the MEML framework need not be taken in isolation when implementing ML models. The constraints of embedded microcontrollers make them a difficult platform to perform training on more complex networks with many parameters, or requiring large amounts of data; however, the MEML software stack can be used in conjunction with other, inference-only libraries such as Tensorflow Lite Micro. A pre-trained model could perform feature extraction to be fed into a smaller, tuneable network: this approach is useful to fine-tune larger networks but also as a way to find and tune mappings between parameter spaces, for example to navigate a RAVE model’s latent space (Privato et al., 2024).

5.2 Future work

Improvements and expansion to the library will follow the requirements of the collaborators and the participants of our validation efforts outlined in Section 4. Feedback from GitHub discussions and community adoption will also be welcome in setting the agenda for future development.

Features that will receive support in future version of the framework are:

- The **internal display** of the MEMLNaut: it will be used to show representations of the weights of parameters of the neural network, further options for tuning the training process (e.g. learning rate, loss visualisation) or more complex reward functions in reinforcement learning.
- **Dataset and model curation**: persistent storage will afford the ability to save and swap models, load them across reboots, and enable more flexible workflows such as training the same model with different datasets, multiple checkpoints, and preset recall.
- Extended software support for **MIDI in/out**.
- Further examples of **audio processing apps**.

Our attention towards lowering the entry barrier to develop for the MEMML ecosystem will bring us to streamline and expand the *meMLP* ML library, to make its API more akin to ‘pythonic’ libraries such as PyTorch or Tensorflow, whilst still supporting a subset of features that are coherent with the goal of ITMLs. The documentation will be enriched with step-by-step tutorials and videos. Finally, research with traditional instrumentalists will lead to insights on how to constrain ML models to make them more suitable for traditional instrumental practice.

6 Conclusions

The work presented here positions Musically Embodied Machine Learning (MEMML) as a response to the long-standing disconnect between embodied musical practice and the largely disembodied workflows of contemporary machine learning systems. By defining Instruments of Tunable Machine Learning (ITML) as self-contained artefacts in which data curation, model training and inference unfold in the same physical and temporal space as performance, we have articulated both a conceptual lens and a practical toolkit. The framework couples an open-source, on-device ML library (*meMLP*) with a low-cost, dual-core RP2350 hardware platform (the MEMLNaut) and a companion *memlib* software layer that abstracts real-time audio, sensor I/O and reinforcement-learning patterns. Through example instruments—a gesture-controlled FM synthesiser and its reinforcement-learning variant—we demonstrate how the framework lowers prototyping barriers, supports artist-in-the-loop experimentation, and invites new forms of dialogue between performer and model. Initial validation in a three-day workshop confirmed both the creative affordances of ITMLs and the pedagogical value of exposing ML concepts through an instrument-centred lens.

Future work will enhance the immediacy of ITMLs and broaden their reach. We plan to add clearer visual feedback, integrate on-device facilities for saving and sharing models, and expand tutorial and teaching materials. Research will explore how adaptable edge models can interact with larger pre-trained systems and how design constraints influence musical expressivity across genres. By working openly with artists, educators and makers, we aim to foster a growing ecosystem in which musical practice and machine learning continually inform one another.

Ethics Statement

Ethics permission for conducting this research when it involved human participants was approved by the University of Sussex’s Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTS), reference: ER/CK84/6.

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